

EXPEDITION REPORT

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Mountain ghosts: protecting snow leopards and other animals of the Tien Shan mountains of Kyrgyzstan

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Abstract

This study is part of an ongoing annual citizen science expedition to investigate snow leopard *Panthera uncia* and various physical, biological and social aspects that affect the species' conservation. The snow leopard expedition has been active for 20 years, making it one of the longest-running initiatives organised by Biosphere Expeditions and one of the most extended research projects on snow leopards ever conducted.

Initially, expeditions were based in the Altai mountain range in Russia from 2003 to 2011, where they utilised sign rates and sightings for species recordings to confirm snow leopard presence, which contributed to the establishment of [Saylyugemsky National Park](#). From 2014 to 2023, expeditions moved to the Kyrgyz Ala-Too area (Karakol valley) of the Tien Shan mountain range and adopted new methodologies that included grid-cell surveys and analysis, as well as camera trapping. Grid-cell analysis enables species distribution conclusions (as opposed to only presence-absence information) while also drastically reducing data autocorrelation. The Kyrgyz Ala-Too expeditions also confirmed snow leopard presence and studied their distribution. However, there was little appetite for establishing community-based protected areas there, so in 2024, the expedition moved to the Teskey Ala-Too range (Burkhan and Archaly valleys), south of Issyk-Kul Lake and near Sarychat-Eertash Nature Reserve.

Results from previous expeditions have recorded snow leopards, scoring from zero to five counts and/or cells annually, mostly by tracks, sighting and more recently also by camera traps (since 2018) and DNA scatology (since 2022). The same methods were applied to record other species of interest, all to identify distributional range as an alternative variable to abundance, which in turn is informative of habitat quality. Species of interest include those that (1) when present, are highly detectable by the methods employed, meaning that a substantial dataset can be obtained to infer eventual fluctuation of populations and (2) are likely to be detected when present, but are often not indicative of habitat modification and human interference.

Records so far indicate that ibex is the most common prey of the snow leopard, followed by marmot, argali, hare and snowcock. The argali has been recorded with decreasing frequency at all study sites. Of all remaining relevant mammals present at the study sites, the wolf is the most prevalent, whereas lynx, wild boar, red deer, musk deer, wolverine and bear signs are rarely recorded. Previous expeditions also published surveys on birds, butterflies, plants, petroglyphs and modelled habitat quality using GIS.

The current expedition was conducted from 8 July to 17 August 2024. The total area sampled was 536 square kilometres, divided into 134 sampling units (cells), 2x2 kilometres in size, with elevations ranging from 2797 to 4395 metres. Sampling lasted 40 days and engaged a total of 36 citizen scientists over three consecutive two-week-long groups. The area covered comprised varied topography, from valleys to mountain ridges and escarpments. Herder interviews, capacity-building and education initiatives were also part of the expedition. Most of the cells (=93%) were sampled just once.

Snow leopards were recorded in seven cells, by means of DNA scatology, camera trapping and track identification. Of the 15 scats collected and presumed to be of snow leopard, DNA analysis revealed that only four were actually from snow leopard (the rest originated from Mongolian wolf *Canis lupus chanco*). Camera traps were put in place by a reconnaissance expedition in July/August 2023 and left operational year-round, yielding 18 snow leopard photos by four camera traps, twelve from August/September 2023 and six from August 2024. Analysis of these photos shows that two, perhaps three, snow leopards of unknown sex populate the study site, which fits well with home ranges published in the literature. Further studies are needed to elucidate individuals by camera trapping and by DNA analysis, as well as whether these animals are transient or resident.

The marmot was the most frequently recorded prey species (96 cells), followed by ibex (34 cells). Moles (29 cells) and hares (16 cells) also had high scores. Argali, on the other hand, was recorded in only three cells, from scats (not confirmed by DNA analysis) and carcasses. Badger (25 cells) and wolf (10 cells) were the most recorded carnivores. Evidence of poaching of ibex and argali combined was found in six cells.

Finally, 16 local households (out of a total of 93) were visited to interview shepherds. Most were found to be open to snow leopard presence as long as this did not impact on livestock grazing. They were also open to alternative incomes through tourism (the expedition is the only type of 'tourism' present apart from a few long-distance cyclists passing through) and as such worked with the expedition to supply food, handicrafts and services such as advice and guiding. Interviews and field work showed that poaching of game ungulates and overgrazing by large herds of sheep, each in their thousands, were the two most significant threats to the snow leopard.

In summary, the results of wildlife presence and richness found in this study site largely agree with previous expeditions results elsewhere in Central Asia. Snow leopards, however, have been recorded more often and the study site was found to be a significant snow leopard habitat, which could develop into a snow leopard stronghold if the two main threats of game ungulate poaching and significant overgrazing by oversized herds could be tackled.

Корутунду

Бул изилдөө ак илбирстерди (*Panthera uncia*) жана аларды сактап калууга таасирин тийгизген ар кандай физикалык, биологиялык жана социалдык аспектилерди изилдөөгө багытталган жарандык илимпоздор тарабынан жылыга жүргүзүлүп жаткан илимий экспедициянын бир бөлүгү болуп саналат. "Илбирс" экспедициясы 20 жылдан бери иштеп жатат. Бул жагынан илбирстерди изилдөөгө багытталган экспедициялардын арасынан эң узакка созулган иш-чаралардын катарын толуктайт.

Алгач 2003-2011-жылдары экспедициялар Россиянын Алтай тоо массивинде жайгашып, ак илбирстин бар экендигин тасыктоо жана байырлаган түрлөрдү аныктоо үчүн белгилердин көрсөткүчтөр жана байкоолор колдонулган, бул өз кезегинде "Сайлугем" улуттук паркынын түзүлүшүнө өбөлгө түзгөн. 2014-жылдан 2023-жылга чейин экспедициялар Тянь-Шань тоо системасындагы Кыргыз Ала-Тоосунун (Батыш Каракол суусунун өрөөнү) аймагына көчүрүлүп келинип, изилдөөдө жаңы методология колдонулду. Анда изилдөөдө аймакты клеткаларга ажыратуу ыкмасы алынган маалыматтардын жаныбарлардын түрлөрүнүн таралышы жөнүндө тыянак чыгарууга мүмкүндүк берет (түрлөрдүн бар болгону жана жоктугу жөнүндө маалыматтан айырмаланат), ошондой эле маалыматтардын автокорреляциясын кыйла азайтат. Кыргыз Ала-Тоосундагы экспедициялардын негизинде ак илбирстин бар экендигин тастыктап, анын таралышы иликтенди. Бирок, ал жерде жамааттык корголуучу аймактарды түзүүгө өзгөчө кызыгуу болгон эмес, ошондуктан 2024-жылы экспедиция Тескей Ала-Тоо кыркаларындагы (Буркан жана Арчалы өрөөндөрү) жана Ысык-Көлдүн түштүк тарабындагы Сарычат-Эрташ мамлекеттик коругуна жакын жерге жайгаштырылган.

Мурунку экспедициялардын жыйынтыгы боюнча, ак илбирстер жыл сайын нөлдөн бешке чейин, негизинен издерден, байкоолордон жана акыркы убакта камера тузактарынан (2018-жылдан) жана ДНК анализинен (2022-жылдан) көбөйүп бара жатканы аныкталган. Ушул эле ыкмалар кызыгууну жараткан башка түрлөрдү эсепке алуу үчүн колдонулган жана алардын бардыгы жаныбарлардын санынын альтернативдүү өзгөрмөсү катары таралуу диапазонун аныктоого багытталган, ал өз кезегинде жашоо чөйрөсүнүн сапатын аныктоо үчүн маалыматтык негиз болуп саналат. Кызыгууну жараткан түрлөргө (1) бар экендиги аныкталган, колдонулган ыкмалар менен оңой табыла турган түрлөр кирет, бул популяциялардын санынын мүмкүн болгон өзгөрүүлөрүн аныктоо үчүн олуттуу көлөмдөгү маалыматтарды алууга болот жана (2) бар экендиги анык болгон учурда табылышы мүмкүн, бирок көбүнчө жашоо чөйрөсүнүн өзгөрүшүн жана антропогендик таасирди көрсөтпөйт.

Бүгүнкү күндө колдо бар маалыматтар эчки-теке илбирстин эң кеңири тараган олжосу экенин, андан кийин суур, аркар-кулжа, толай коену жана улар экенин көрсөтүп турат. Бардык изилдөөлөрдүн жыйынтыгы боюнча аркар-кулжалардын санынын азайып бара жаткандыгы байкалат. Изилдөө жүргүзүлгөн аймактагы башка маанилүү сүт эмүүчүлөрдүн ичинен карышкыр эң көп таралган. Ал эми сүлөөсүн, каман, марал, мускус бугусу, карышкыр жана аюунун белгилери сейрек кездешет. Мындан сырткары мурунку экспедицияларда канаттууларды, көпөлөктөрдү, өсүмдүктөрдү, петроглифтерди ГИСТИ колдонуу менен жашоо чөйрөсүнүн сапатынын модели жүргүзүлгөн.

Каралып жаткан экспедиция 2024-жылдын 8-июлунан 17-августуна чейин жүргүзүлдү. Изилденген аймак узуну, туурасы 2x2 километр болгон 134 клеткага бөлүнүп, жалпы аянты 536 чарчы километрди түздү. Абсолюттук бийиктиги 2797 метрден 4395 метрге чейин жетет. Жалпысынан 40 күндүн ичинде маалыматтар топтолду жана эки жумалык үч экспедицияга жалпысынан 36 жарандык илимпоз катышты. Изилденген аймактын рельефи өрөөндөрдөн тоо кыркаларына жана аскаларга чейин өзгөрөт. Экспедиция учурунда эле малчылар менен маек жүргүзүлүп, кызматташуу потенциалын жогорулатуу жана агартуу иш-чаралары өткөрүлдү. Көпчүлүк клеткалар (n=93%) болгону бир жолу текшерилген.

Аймакта ак илбирстер ДНК анализи, камера тузактары жана издерди идентификациялоонун жардамы менен жети клеткада аныкталды. Ак илбирске тиешелүү деп болжолдонгон 15 кыктын ичинен ДНК анализи төртөө гана ак илбирске таандык (калгандары Монгол карышкырына таандык) экендиги аныктады. Камера тузактары экспедиция тарабынан 2023-жылдын июль-август айларында жайгаштырылып, жыл бою иштеген. Алардын ичинен төрт камера тузагы ак илбирстин 18 сүрөтүн тартып алды. Алардын он экиси 2023-жылдын август - сентябрь, алтоосу 2024-жылдын август айында тартылган. Бул сүрөттөрдү талдоо менен, изилденип жаткан аймакта жынысы белгисиз эки же үч ак илбирстин байырлагандыгы аныкталды. Бул жыйынтык мурда жарыяланган адабияттарда көрсөтүлгөн ак илбирстердин чөйрөсүнө дал келет. Бул жаныбарлардын убактылуу же туруктуу жашоочу экенин камера тузактары жана ДНК анализи аркылуу аныктоо үчүн кошумча изилдөөлөр талап кылынат.

Изилдөө аймагында суур эң көп кездешкен түр (96 клеткада аныкталды) экендиги аныкталды, андан кийинки орунда эчки-теке (34 клетка) болгон. Сокур чычкандар (29 клетка) жана толай коендору (16 клетка) да көп кездешүүчү белгилерге ээ болушкан. Аркар-кулжалар болсо үч клеткада кыктарынан (ДНК анализинде тастыкталбаган) жана сөөктөрдүн жардамы менен гана табылган. Жырткычтардын арасынан кашкулак (25 клетка) жана карышкыр (10 клетка) эң көп катталган. Алты клеткада эчки-теке менен аркар-кулжага карата браконьерликтин далилдери табылган.

Акырында, малчыларды сурамжылоо үчүн жарандык илимпоздор 16 жергиликтүү туракка (жалпы 93) барышты. Малчылардын көбү малга кол салмайынча ак илбирс менен канатташ жашаганга даяр экени аныкталды. Ошондой эле малчылар туризм аркылуу альтернативалуу киреше табуу үчүн ачык болушкан (экспедиция - бул алыскы аймактарга каттаган велосипедчилерди кошпогондо аймактагы "туризмдин" жалгыз түрү), ошондуктан экспедиция менен кызматташып, тамак-аш, кол өнөр буюмдары жана консультация жана коштоо сыяктуу кызматтарды камсыз кылышкан. Сурамжылоолор жана талаа изилдөөлөрү көрсөткөндөй, туяктуу жаныбарларга браконьерлик жүргүзүү жана ар бири миңдеп саналган кой үйүрлөрүнүн ыксыз жайылуусу ак илбирс үчүн эң олуттуу эки коркунуч болуп саналат.

Жыйынтыктап айтканда, бул изилдөө учурунда табылган жапайы жаратылыштын бар болуусу жана байлыгы тууралуу корутундулар Борбордук Азиянын башка аймактарына болгон мурунку экспедициялардын жыйынтыктарына дал келет. Бирок, ак илбирстер көп катталган жана изилдөө жүргүзүлгөн аймактын ак илбирс байырлаган бирден бир маанилүү ареал экендиги аныкталган. Эгерде ак илбирстерге карата эки негизги коркунучтуу - туяктуу жаныбарларга жүргүзүлгөн мыйизимсыз аңчылык жана малдын ири үйүрлөрүнүн ыксыз жайылуусу чектелсе, бул аймак ак илбирстин таянычына айланышы толук ыктымал.

Резюме

Данное исследование является частью продолжающейся ежегодной гражданской научной экспедиции, направленной на изучение снежного барса *Panthera uncia* и различных физических, биологических и социальных аспектов, влияющих на сохранение этого вида. Экспедиция "Снежный барс" существует уже 20 лет, что делает ее одной из самых продолжительных инициатив, организованных Биосферными экспедициями, и одним из самых продолжительных исследовательских проектов по снежному барсу, когда-либо проводившихся.

Первоначально, с 2003 по 2011 год, экспедиции базировались в горном массиве Алтай в России, где были использованы показатели признаков и наблюдения для выявления видов, чтобы подтвердить присутствие снежного барса, что способствовало созданию "Сайлюгемского" национального парка. С 2014 по 2023 год экспедиции переместились в район горного хребта Кыргызского Ала-Тоо (долина реки Западный Каракол) горной системы Тянь-Шань и внедрились новые методологии, которые включали съемку с использованием ячеек сетки и анализ, а также съемку с помощью фотоловушек. Анализ по ячейкам сетки позволяет делать выводы о распределении видов (в отличие от информации только о присутствии и отсутствии), а также значительно сокращает автокорреляцию данных. Экспедиции в Кыргызском Ала-Тоо также подтвердили присутствие снежного барса и изучили его распределение. Однако в данной местности не было особого желания создавать общинные охраняемые территории, поэтому в 2024 году экспедиция перебазировалась на хребет Тескей Ала-Тоо (долины Бурхан и Арчалы), к югу от озера Иссык-Куль и недалеко от Сарычат-Эрташского государственного заповедника.

По результатам предыдущих экспедиций было зафиксировано, что снежные барсы ежегодно набирают численность или выявляемых клеток от нуля до пяти, в основном по следам, при наблюдении, а в последнее время также с помощью фотоловушек (с 2018 года) и ДНК-анализа (с 2022 года). Те же методы были применены для выявления других представляющих интерес видов, и все они были направлены на определение ареала распространения как альтернативной переменной численности, которая, в свою очередь, является информативной для определения качества среды обитания. К представляющим интерес видам относятся те, которые (1) при наличии легко обнаруживаются с помощью используемых методов, что означает, что может быть получен значительный объем данных для определения возможных колебаний численности популяций, и (2) вероятно, будут обнаружены при наличии, но часто не указывают на изменение среды обитания и антропогенного влияния.

Имеющиеся на сегодняшний день данные свидетельствуют о том, что горный козел является наиболее распространенной добычей снежного барса, за ним следуют сурок, архар, толай-заяц и улар. Количество архаров на всех участках исследования сокращается. Из всех остальных значимых млекопитающих, присутствующих в местах проведения исследований, волк является наиболее распространенным, в то время как признаки обитания рыси, дикого кабана, благородного оленя, кабарги, россомахи и медведя регистрируются редко. Предыдущие экспедиции также опубликовали обзоры птиц, бабочек, растений, петроглифов и моделировали качество среды обитания с использованием ГИС-технологии.

Нынешняя экспедиция проводилась с 8 июля по 17 августа 2024 года. Общая площадь исследования составила 536 квадратных километров и была разделена на 134 единицы отбора проб (ячейки) размером 2х2 километра с высотами от 2797 до 4395 метров. Данные получены в течение 40 дней, и в трех двухнедельных экспедициях подряд приняли участие в общей сложности 36 гражданских ученых. Местность, которую они обследовали, отличалась разнообразным рельефом - от долин до горных хребтов и обрывов. В рамках экспедиции также проводились беседы с пастухами, мероприятия по наращиванию потенциала в области сотрудничества и просвещения. Большинство ячеек ($n=93\%$) были исследованы всего один раз.

Снежные барсы были выявлены в семи ячейках с помощью ДНК анализа, фотоловушек и идентификации следов. Из 15 собранных экскрементов, предположительно принадлежавших снежному барсу, анализ ДНК показал, что только четыре в действительности принадлежали снежному барсу (остальные относились к монгольскому волку *Canis lupus chanco*). Фотоловушки были установлены предварительной экспедицией в июле-августе 2023 года и работали круглый год. Четыре фотоловушки позволили получить 18 фотографий снежного барса, двенадцать из которых были сделаны в августе-сентябре 2023 года, а шесть - в августе 2024 года. Анализ этих фотографий показывает, что на исследуемой территории обитают два, а может быть, и три снежных барса неизвестного пола, что хорошо согласуется с опубликованными в литературе ареалами обитания. Необходимы дальнейшие исследования, чтобы выявить особей с помощью фотоловушек и анализа ДНК, а также определить, являются ли эти животные временными или постоянными обитателями данной местности.

Сурок был наиболее часто встречаемым видом (96 ячеек), за ним следовал горный козел (34 ячейки). Кроты (29 ячеек) и толай-зайцы (16 ячеек) также получили высокие маркировки. Архары, с другой стороны, были обнаружены только в трех ячейках, из экскрементов (не подтвержденных анализом ДНК) и костей. Барсук (25 клеток) и волк (10 клеток) были самыми распространенными хищниками. В шести клетках были обнаружены свидетельства браконьерской охоты на горного козла и архара вместе взятых.

Наконец, были посещены 16 местных стойбищ (из общего числа 93), чтобы провести опросы пастухов. Было установлено, что большинство из них были готовы к присутствию снежного барса до тех пор, пока он не нападал на домашний скот. Они также были открыты для получения альтернативных доходов за счет туризма (экспедиция - это единственный вид "туризма", который существует в настоящее время, не считая осмотра достопримечательностей, по которым проезжают велосипедисты на дальние расстояния), и поэтому сотрудничали с экспедицией, поставляя продукты питания, изделия ручной работы и услуги, такие как консультации и сопровождение. Интервью и полевые исследования показали, что браконьерство на копытных животных и чрезмерный выпас скота большими отарами овец, каждая из которых насчитывает тысячи особей, были двумя наиболее серьезными угрозами для снежного барса.

Таким образом, результаты о присутствии и богатстве дикой природы, обнаруженные на этом исследовательском участке, в значительной степени согласуются с результатами предыдущих экспедиций в другие районы Центральной Азии. Однако пребывание снежных барсов выявили яснее, и было установлено, что место проведения исследований является значительным местом обитания снежного барса, которое может превратиться в оплот снежного барса, если удастся устранить две основные угрозы - браконьерство на копытных и значительный перевыпас скота крупными стадами.

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1. Expedition Review

M. Hammer (editor)
Biosphere Expeditions

1.1. Background

This study was part of an ongoing annual citizen science expedition to study snow leopards *Panthera uncia* and physical, biological and social aspects that affect the species. Biosphere Expeditions has worked in snow leopard research and conservation in Central Asia for over two decades, collecting information on the biology of species and making key alliances with conservation organizations and local communities. These efforts have resulted in substantial knowledge gained on the biotic aspects of the sampled areas, stable alliances with conservation NGOs and the support of local people and communities in data collection year-round.

Expeditions in Central Asia were first based in the Altai mountain range in Russia from 2003 to 2011. From 2014 onwards, expeditions moved to the Tien Shan mountains in Kyrgyzstan, first to Karakol valley in the Kyrgyz Ala-Too range (2014-2023), and most recently to Burkhan & Archaly valleys in the Teskey Ala-Too range (Figure 1.1a).

Figure 1.1a. Schematic map of current and previous snow leopard expedition sites in Central Asia.

1.2. Research area

Kyrgyzstan is a country located in Central Asia, which is often referred to as the "Switzerland of Central Asia". Landlocked and mountainous, Kyrgyzstan is bordered by Kazakhstan to the north, China to the southeast, Tajikistan to the southwest and Uzbekistan to the west. Its capital and largest city is Bishkek.

The Tien Shan is the largest mountain range in Asia by surface area, stretching 2,800 km from Uzbekistan in the west to China and Mongolia in the east. With a maximum width of 800 km, it is surrounded by deserts, and composed of sedimentary, metamorphic and igneous rocks. It is also the highest mountain range within arid extratropical Asia, reaching 7,439 m at its highest peak (Baldwin & Vecchi 2016). Amidst this chronically water-stressed region of the world, water melt from glaciers, especially from the Tien Shan, provides a key water resource that creates some resilience against seasonal and interannual precipitation variations (Aizen & Aizen 1997, Aizen 2011).

The Tien Shan forms an ecological bridge that loosely connects the mountain ranges of South Asia, including the Himalaya, Pamir and Hindu Kush, with the remote, Inner Asian ranges of Mongolia and Siberia, most notably the Altai and Sayan mountains. Because of this geographic positioning and the increasingly arid environment of the surrounding region, the Tien Shan serves as an important corridor for the movement and dispersal of mountain-dwelling species between the ranges of Inner and South Asia. It is also a meeting place for the flora and fauna of Central Asia, Inner Asia, Tibet, South Asia, and even East Asia, Europe and the Mediterranean.

Over 80 percent of Kyrgyzstan is covered by the Tien Shan mountains, which harbour varying extents of glaciers and permafrost. More than half of the country is above 2,500 m. The remaining landscape comprises valleys and basins, all covered by either steppe or alpine vegetation.

Kyrgyzstan has many different climates, but the most prevalent ones are Hot Humid Continental Climate (Köppen-Geiger Dsa) and Cold Semi-Arid Climate (Köppen-Geiger BSk).

The Kyrgyz Tien Shan together with the Pamirs of Tajikistan play a crucial role as the primary water catchments for almost all of former Soviet Central Asia, as well as for large parts of western Xinjiang (China). These catchments are the sources of the two largest rivers flowing to the depleted Aral Sea, the Syr Darya and the Amu Darya. These water sources allow large populations to exist in the arid region and are of key importance to national economies, which are heavily dependent on irrigation-intensive agricultural systems.

The most important rivers, which have all, or portions of, their headwaters within Kyrgyz territory, do not flow to the sea. The Syr Darya and Amu Darya are the lifeblood of the agricultural economies of Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan and western Kazakhstan, and the misuse of these has led to the present Aral Sea crisis (Micklin 2007). The Naryn River is the longest and most important river in Kyrgyzstan and is one of two rivers originating on Kyrgyz territory that join in the Ferghana Valley of Uzbekistan to form the Syr Darya, the other being the Kara Darya, which originates in Osh province.

The Naryn river (Figure 1.2a), running south of the study area, gathers high in the tundra bogs of the Ak-Shirak Range, at an elevation of about 3,800 m, flowing roughly 600 km to Uzbekistan, filling three major reservoirs en route, which are the source of much of Kyrgyzstan's electricity.

Snow and glacier melt are an extremely important part of the hydrological cycle in the Tien Shan, with glacier melt alone accounting for, on average, about 10 percent of flow from mountain streams, which can increase to 20 percent during times of drought. The single longest glacier in these icefields is the Engilchek Glacier, which is 58 km in length.

Despite the immense amount of water coming from glaciers and permafrost areas, clean water is becoming a scarce resource. The vast Kumtor open pit gold mine pollutes an area next to the Sarychat-Ertash reserve and not far from Issyk-Kul (Ysyk-Köl) lake. The open-pit mine sits in fragile permafrost and in the vicinity of glaciers that feed fresh waters into the transboundary Naryn River.

Further, with the growing need of electricity, there have also been issues over the use of water for electricity, irrigation and home use (Nikanorova et al. 2016).

Figure 1.2a. Study area in Kyrgyzstan.

There are many threatened animal and plant species present in the area, a great number of them endemic, with a recent count showing at least 70 threatened mammal, 376 bird, 44 fish and 3,000 insect species.

The Kyrgyz people are descendants of several different nomadic Turkic ethnic groups in Central Asia and were first mentioned in writing in 201 BC. Kyrgyzstan is one of the active members of the Turkic Council and the TÜRKSOY community. Kyrgyzstan's history is one of Turkic, Mongol, and more recently Soviet and Russian domination. Independence from the Soviet Union was declared on 31 August 1991 and Kyrgyzstan became, and has stayed, a democratic country.

During the Soviet era, the principal industries of Kyrgyzstan were the production of wool and meat, uranium and tin mining, some textile factories and industrial production. With independence in 1991, almost all of these industries collapsed, and people were forced into self-employed subsistence occupations, such as being small farmers and livestock owners, or small traders shuttling back and forth between China, Kazakhstan and Russia. Few new industries have emerged in Kyrgyzstan since, although the country has been opened to international mining investment, and the Canadian-owned Kumtor gold mine, one of the world's largest, now accounts for about nine percent of overall Kyrgyz GDP.

In the highlands of Kyrgyzstan, many species have been pushed to the brink of local extinction since the onset of the economic crisis of the 1990s, which hit rural areas particularly hard. Disbandment of agricultural collectives left entire villages without state support. In efforts to generate cash incomes or simply survive, many Kyrgyz turned to hunting, including the widespread poaching of endangered species, which resulted in a severe reduction of wild animal populations. In the 1980s the Kyrgyz Republic and neighboring Tajikistan were estimated to harbor 20 percent of the global snow leopard population, which is suspected to have declined by 75 percent in the 1990s after the fall of the Soviet Union (Koshkarev&Vyrypaev 2000). By 1996 the estimated population of snow leopards had fallen by half or more to an estimated 650 individuals, as animals were trapped for fur and the sale of body parts for traditional Chinese medicine, while live cubs were sold to private zoos. In 2003, it was estimated that as few as 150 snow leopards remained in Kyrgyzstan (Vorobeev& Van der Ven 2003).

Nomenclature and distribution of species follow the IUCN Red List (IUCN 2024), which may slightly differ from previous literature. Most important prey species for the snow leopard *Panthera uncia* present in the study area are the argali or Marco Polo sheep *Ovis ammon*, Siberian ibex *Capra sibirica* and the Altai marmot *Marmota baibacina*. Relevant carnivore species are the brown bear *Ursus arctos*, Eurasian lynx *Lynx lynx*, grey wolf *Canis lupus*, Asian badger *Meles leucurus* and Pallas's cat *Otocolobus manul*.

1.3. Dates & team

The expedition ran over a period of six weeks divided into three 13-day group rotations, each composed of a team of national and international citizen scientists, a professional scientist and an expedition leader. Group dates were as shown in the team list below.

The expedition team was recruited by Biosphere Expeditions and consisted of a mixture of ages, nationalities and backgrounds. They were (in alphabetical order and with country of residence):

8 – 20 July 2024

Raja Azwina (Malaysia), Elke Fischer (Germany), Seema Issar (Germany), Lyra Jackewitz (Germany), Ann-Marie Kegelmaier (Germany), Claus Ludwig (Germany), Olivia Mollatz (Austria), Samy Moussally (Switzerland), Florian Niggel (Germany), Stefan Niggel (Germany), Thomas Panzl (Austria), Iyer Subbalakshmi (USA).

22 July – 3 August 2024

Axel Bachmann (Germany), Jill Cole (UK), Elena Dormer (Australia), Gerald Duda (Germany), Danielle Georgelin (Australia), John Hippe (Germany), Ernst Klungler (Germany), Stefanie Mannweiler (Germany), Tanja Meurer (Germany), Kerry Richmond (USA), Gina Rogers (USA), Friedeger Stierle (Germany), Evgeny Strelnikov (USA).

5 – 17 August 2024

David Baumgartner (Switzerland), Shani Baumgartner (Switzerland), Jörg Boysen (Germany), Ian Howell (UK), Angelika Krimmel (Germany), Karin Lindner-Vogt (Germany), Kristina Pfülb (Germany), Zoë Poole (Canada), Jaqueline Ridewood (UK), Sebastian Schlegel (Germany), Evgeny Strelnikov (USA).

The expedition scientist and co-author of this report was Emilbek Zholdoshibekov, the expedition leader was Johnny Adams. Also involved were expedition cook Azamat Doolotbekovand; on a rotational basis, members of NABU's anti-poaching patrol Grupa Bars: Bekbolot Ozgorushuulu, Ibraim Asykulov, Mirlan Duishenbaev, Almaz Zhumasydykov and Ayan Dosjanov, all from Kyrgyzstan.

A medical umbrella, safety and evacuation procedures were in place, but did not have to be invoked as there were no health or safety incidences.

1.4. Partners

[NABU](#) (= Naturschutzbund = nature protection alliance), founded in 1899, is one of Germany's oldest and its biggest conservation NGOs. In Kyrgyzstan, NABU, in cooperation with the Kyrgyz government, is implementing a programme to conserve the snow leopard through a twin approach of research and the prevention of illegal hunting and trade of the endangered species (see <http://nabu.kg/wp/>).

1.5. Acknowledgements

We are grateful to the expedition participants, who not only dedicated their spare time to helping but also, through their expedition contributions, funded the research. Thank you also to our partner organization NABU, in particular NABU's Gruppa Bars, and to Maksat Mukanbetov from the study site community for his advice and guidance. Thank you also to Almaz Alzhambaev of www.carforrent.kg, the Friends of Biosphere Expeditions and all donors to a fundraising campaign for their support. Finally, thank you to Dr. Marcelo Mazzolli for significant help with the text and the peer reviewers for helpful comments.

1.6. Further information & enquiries

More background information on Biosphere Expeditions in general and on this expedition in particular including pictures, diary excerpts and more can be found on the Biosphere Expeditions website www.biosphere-expeditions.org. Enquiries should be addressed to Biosphere Expeditions at the address given on the website.

A copy of this and all other reports and scientific publications produced by or in association with this expedition can be found on the [Biosphere Expeditions ResearchGate page](#). A copy of the diary of this expedition is on the [Biosphere Expeditions blog page](#).

1.7. Expedition budget

Each citizen scientist participant paid towards expedition costs a contribution of € 2,890 per person per 13-day group. The contribution covered accommodation and meals, supervision and induction, special research equipment and all transport from and to the team assembly point. It did not cover excess luggage charges, travel insurance, personal expenses such as telephone bills, souvenirs etc., or visa and other travel expenses to and from the assembly point (e.g. international flights). Details on how this contribution was spent are given below.

Income	€
Expedition contributions	56,583
 Expenditure	
Expedition base includes all food & services	11,443
Transport includes hire cars, fuel, taxis in Kyrgyzstan	10,338
Equipment and hardware includes research materials & gear etc. purchased internationally & locally	4,768
Staff includes local and Biosphere Expeditions staff salaries and travel expenses	14,054
Administration includes miscellaneous fees & sundries	1,478
Team recruitment Tien Shan as estimated % of annual PR costs for Biosphere Expeditions	9,768
 Income – Expenditure	 4,734
 Total percentage spent directly on project	 92%

2. Monitoring snow leopards and other species on the south side of the Teskey Ala-Too mountain range in the Tien Shan mountains of Kyrgyzstan

Marcelo Mazzolli
Biosphere Expeditions

Emilbek Zholdosbekov
Ala-Too International University

2.1. Introduction

Twenty-one years of continuous snow leopard research

This study is part of an ongoing annual citizen science expedition to study snow leopards *Panthera uncia*. Expeditions were first based in the Altai mountain range in Russia from 2003 to 2011. From 2014 onwards, expeditions moved to the Tien Shan mountains in Kyrgyzstan, first to Karakol valley in the Kyrgyz Ala-Too range (2014-2023), and most recently to Burkhan & Archaly valleys in the Teskey Ala-Too range (Figure 1.1a), where a reconnaissance expedition with a preliminary survey was done and 16 camera traps were left in the mountains in July/August 2023. This report summarises the first full expedition - in 2024 - that worked exclusively at the new site.

Developing research methodologies

Despite the challenges, such as having to leave Russia due to political issues (mainly Putin's notorious [foreign agents law](#)) and periodic variations in study design, analysis and reporting (due to changing expedition scientists), results of the expeditions make a valuable contribution to snow leopard research. Conservation research is all about observing patterns and trends, which can be compared with other results in the biological literature. Since Biosphere Expeditions has (1) formed stable partnerships with local communities for collaborative work, a crucial step in successful conservation outcomes, and (2) run expeditions over two decades, which is a long time for conservation projects, the conditions for comparative long-term studies are there and detailed in this report.

Often, as is the case on many occasions, and mainly during the initial expeditions, information on the biology of the cryptic snow leopard was scarce. That is when analysis of habitat, which includes the presence of prey and other wildlife, is important. By analysing the presence of prey and other sympatric species, plus evaluation of disturbances, quality of habitat for the snow leopard may be inferred (e.g. Mazzolli 2009). In addition, snow leopard distribution may be defined by the distribution of its main prey species (e.g. Lukarevsky et al. 2019, Tytar et al. 2019, Lham et al. 2021).

Prey species as indicators of snow leopard distribution and habitat quality

One of the main eye-catching research results of Biosphere Expeditions in Central Asia, besides recording snow leopards, is the substantial amount of data for ibex and argali. They are the two most conspicuous, widespread and important wild prey ungulates found at the study sites.

The foundation of the snow leopard's diet is large ungulates, but wild ungulates are scattered and difficult to catch. Small mammals and birds are more readily available, supplementary food items, filling the gaps between ungulate kills. Lukarevsky et al. (2019) showed that marmot *Marmota baibacina* is an important small prey species in the summer diet of snow leopards in three different study sites of Mongolia's Altai range. Marmots have also been extensively observed by Biosphere Expeditions and are thus included as a species to determine habitat quality. Snow leopard also prey on other small mammals, including hares *Lepus timidus* and *L. tibetanus*. Bird prey species include Altai snowcock *Tetraogallus altaicus* and *T. himalayensis*, and chukar partridge *Alectoris chukar* (Oli et al. 1993, Lhagvasuren & Munkhtsog 2000).

Snow leopards, livestock, shepherds and grazing: a ubiquitous threat

All expeditions took place in non-protected areas (even if the Altai expeditions eventually contributed to the establishment of [Saylyugemsky National Park](#)), where grazing of livestock is ubiquitous, and the current expedition is no exception. Because of the lack of regulations or enforcement of existing regulations, overgrazing was found to be an issue on all but the Altai expeditions. The presence of humans with temporary dwellings, herding dogs, vehicles, horses and livestock is a constant source of disturbance and manifold threats, especially during the summer grazing months, when the expeditions take place. Snow leopards and their prey are threatened by competition for space and food, retaliatory killings, poaching, legal and illegal trophy hunting, to name but a few.

2.2. Materials and methods

Study area

The expedition study area is in eastern Kyrgyzstan, in the mountain range known as Teskey Ala-Too range, which is part of the Tien Shan mountains. It is located in the district of Ton Rayon of the Ysyk-Kol province. The nearest settlements are Jer-Kochku (70 km to the east) Bokonbaev (50 km to the north) and Barskoon (90 km from the north-east). The distance from Bishkek is 250 km and from Kochkor 170 km (Figure 2.2a). Base camp was in Burkhan valley (Figure 2.2b).

The general topography consists of mountain ranges and intermountain depressions that run parallel from east to west. This specific alpine type of landforms was formed by new tectonic activities and by fluvial, glacial erosions.

The region is characterised by a marked continental climate, with an average annual air temperature of -7°C . Winter temperatures can drop to -40°C , with more frost than snow. Average air temperatures for July and August, when expedition takes place, vary between 3.5 and 5°C . Summer is short and cool. During daytime, air temperature can reach 20 - 25°C due to high solar radiation (Oroskojoev 1982).

Precipitation is limited (300-350 mm) and happens mostly during summer (50 to 70 mm for each summer month). Air humidity varies from 43 to 68 percent. Western winds are predominant.

Snow cover is present 200 days per year at an average thickness of 35-50 cm. Above 3,300 m there is permafrost, which is reflected on the surface as solifluction (slow downslope movement of soil due to recurrent freezing and thawing of the ground).

Vegetation and snow cover vary with altitude. There are glaciers and perennial snow ($\geq 3,600$ m), high mountain desert (3,200-4,000 m), alpine meadow (3,500-4,000 m), subalpine meadow (3,000-3,500 m) and steppe ($\leq 3,000$ m).

The hydrographic system is dominated by the Naryn river and its tributaries, the Kichi, Burkhan, Jyluu-Suu and Archaly rivers (Figures 2.2a and 2.2b). Base camp sits next to the Burkhan river (Figure 2.2b) on summer pastureland of Bokonbaev village of Ton rayon (district) of the Ysyk-Kol oblast (region).

High mountain pasture lands were assigned to villages during the Soviet era and the lands owned by collective farms. The process of land reform in Kyrgyzstan, as in all former Soviet countries, had to move agriculture from the Soviet model of state-owned land and predominance of large-scale farming enterprises to a market-oriented model of privately-owned land with a predominance of small- and medium-sized family farms (FAO 2009). However, unlike arable land and other collective farm property, pasturelands have not been privatised. Instead they are managed by a local village administration body (pasture committee = aiylokmotu). This pasture committee provides use management, care and repair of pasture as well as organising livestock transfer from winter village stables to summer pastures and back.

Shepherds in the current study site mostly breed sheep, cow, horse and yak. The southern section of the Burkhan River is part of Bokonbayev village and comprises 44 dwellings. The northern section is part of Tort-Kul village and comprises 11 dwellings. Dwellings can be temporary shelters such as yurts, house-tents, wagon-trailers and some brick constructions. Permanent constructions are not allowed on summer pastures. There are usually enclosures around the dwellings for keeping livestock. The grazing season is from the end of May until the end of September. Due to the thin snow cover, the Burkhan and Archaly valleys are also used for winter pastureland and shepherds are breeding livestock for the entire year.

Research methods

The study area (Figure 2.2b & c) was divided into grid cells of 2x2 km size following Mazzolli & Hammer (2013) to identify distributional range as an alternative variable to abundance, which in turn is informative of habitat quality.

The grid used was that of the Military Grid Reference System (MGRS) of the Soviet-era military topographic maps (created in 1969, updated in 1980) at a scale of 1:100,000. Printed topographic maps and GPS models Garmin 64s and Garmin Montana 700i were used in the field.

Figure 2.2a. Topographic and hydrographic network of Kyrgyzstan. Highlighted are the travel route from the capital Bishkek, base camp and study area.

Figure 2.2b. Study area. Terrain shadow and isolines were generated using ALOS PALSAR DEM, glaciers using RGI shapefiles (WGS 84 datum).

Nineteen digital camera traps (Bushnell 8MP and Bushnell 14MP, Figure 2.2c, Appendix I) were installed in locations that Jackson et al. (2006) identified as those with the best chance to capture snow leopards, sixteen of these had been in place since a reconnaissance expedition in 2023 left them there. These places are where leopards are likely to scent-spray and leave their scrapes. Examples are by large boulders, at the base of cliffs, or bends of trails or other well-defined landform edges, where trails are constrained by topography or vegetation.

Snow leopard signs such as tracks, scrapes and scent-sprayed locations were also searched for. Snow leopards can be identified by tracks if prints are clear. However, there is a chance to confuse snow leopard track with those of lynx, although prints of adult snow leopards are larger. Besides size, a lynx track is much more “long-toed” and “thin-toed”, and the paw pad is not as massive, occupying a smaller share of the entire paw print. Unlike the graceful, elongated digital pad impressions of the lynx, those of the snow leopard are more rounded and blunter (Matyushkin & Koshkarev 1990 in Karnaukhov et al. 2020).

Presumed snow leopard scats were collected for DNA analysis, which was performed by the [Senckenberg Institute’s Centre for Wildlife Genetics](#) in Germany. Most other species of interest had their scats identified by sight without confirmation by DNA analysis, which is expensive.

Species of interest included:

- (1) Species that, when present, are highly detectable by the methods employed, meaning that a substantial dataset can be obtained to infer basic population dynamics. Examples include the two key prey species ibex and marmot.
- (2) Species that are likely to be detected when present, but are often not, indicating habitat modification and human interference. Examples include one important prey species, the argali, and also the wolf, lynx, brown bear and deer species. Other species were also circumstantially recorded, such as weasel, vole and badger.

Camera traps, DNA analysis and direct sightings are the most reliable ways to identify species. In addition, species were identified by tracks, burrows, calls and scats. Spatial data were analysed in ESRI ArcGIS 10.8 software. A pansharpened Landsat 8 imagery (acquired on 11 July 2024) georeferenced topography map was used to overlay data. The map was then given a terrain shadow effect, created by ALOS PALSAR DEM, to highlight differences in topography.

Figure 2.2c. Map of the study area showing the 134 2 x 2 km cells surveyed, with rivers, expedition base camp, camera trap locations, and unpaved roads.

Terrain shadow generated by using ALOS PAL-SAR DEM.

Legend

- | | | | |
|------------------------------------|---------------|-----------------|--------------------------|
| Surveyed grid cells researched by: | | — Main rivers | ● Camera traps from 2023 |
| ■ Pilot study | ■ Group no. 2 | — Rivers | △ Base camp |
| ■ Group no. 1 | ■ Group no. 3 | — Unpaved roads | |

Shepherd interviews

Three to four expeditioners (including an interpreter) conducted shepherd interviews using a [standardised interview datasheet](#) within an informal, casual conversation. The expedition adhered to the working strategy of its local partner NABU and their Grupa Bars (snow leopard anti-poaching team) staff members, two of which accompanied each expedition group on a rotational basis. Location of camera traps and other research methods were not shared with local shepherds. Instead – and while conducting interviews – an emphasis was placed on fostering friendly relations in what the expedition scientist termed “Kymyz (local specialty of fermented horse milk) diplomacy”. Conversations with children about the importance of the nature conservation was another focus.

Training of citizen scientists

Training of citizen scientists involved identification of target species and their signs and use of GPS during the first two (training) days of each expedition rotation. On days two and three citizen scientists were accompanied into the field by staff and surveys conducted in one big group as a data collection training and learning experience. After this, citizen scientists went on surveys by themselves in small groups, with different expedition groups concentrating on different areas (see Figure 2.2c). GPSs were loaded with the 2x2 km grid so that data could be recorded in the correct location and the groups were able to know how much terrain and how many cells they had covered. Each survey group was tasked to cover a particular area during the day time by the expedition scientists. Groups by and large returned to base for the night, except when the scientist and expedition leader organised overnight trips using mobile satellite camps in order to reach areas further away from base.

Field data were collected in data sheets. Once back at base camp, survey groups presented their field data, analysed them with the help of staff, who then transferred the results to summary sheets and a grid map for each individual species. The summary sheets and an overview map were displayed at camp, with cells being ticked off as they were surveyed, giving the expedition team a visual confirmation of achievements and progress.

2.3. Results

Overall results

The expedition lasted 40 days (8 July – 17 August 2024) and sampled 536 square kilometres, divided into 134 sampling units (cells) 2x2 kilometres in size, with elevations ranging from 2,797 to 4,395 meters. Sampling was conducted by twelve citizen scientists on each rotation (36 citizen scientists in total), as well as two rotating NABU Grupa Bars members per rotation. The expedition scientist and the expedition leader were present throughout and supported survey efforts. The area covered comprised a varied topography, from valleys to mountain ridges and escarpments. Capacity-building and education initiatives were also part of the expedition. Most of the cells (93%) were sampled just once.

Snow leopards were recorded in eight cells, by means of camera trapping, DNA scatology and track identification. Of the 15 scats collected and presumed to be of snow leopards, DNA analysis revealed that four originated from snow leopards and eleven from wolf.

Marmot was the most frequently recorded prey species (96 cells), followed by ibex (34), mole (29) and hare (16). Argali, on the other hand, was recorded in only three cells, from scats and carcasses. Badger (25) and wolf (10) were the most recorded carnivores. Evidence of poaching of ibex and argali was found in seven cells.

Fifteen shepherd camps (out of a total of 93) were visited for interviews. Most shepherds were found to be suspicious of wildlife conservation efforts, most likely because they have concerns that this would reveal their own poaching activities, which include retaliatory killings and efforts to create favourable conditions for their large (over)grazing herds.

Snow leopard *Panthera uncia*

Snow leopard was recorded in eight cells, by camera trapping (four cells), DNA scatology (five cells) and tracking (one cell), with some cells recoding snow leopard by multiple methods (Table 2.3a, Figure 2.3a).

Table 2.3a. Snow leopard detections by the expedition.

Cell	Detection method	No of detections	Altitude (m)	Habitat	Remarks
L-12	Camera trap BE06	3 photos of 1 individual	3982	Mountain ridge	Trap in place Aug 2023* – July 2024, photo capture on 18.08.2023 at 03:56
L-12	Camera trap BE06	3 photos of 1 individual	3982	Mountain ridge	Trap in place Aug 2023* – July 2024, photo capture on 30.08.2023 at 07:12
O-13	Camera trap BE07	6 photos of 1 individual	3718	Mountain ridge	Trap in place Aug 2023* – August 2024, photo capture on 04.08.2024 at 21:04
P-09	Camera trap BE35	3 photos of 1 individual	3822	Mountain ridge	Trap in place Aug 2023* – July 2024, photo capture on 28.09.2023 at 03:42
P-14	Camera trap BE20	3 photos of 1 individual	3841	Mountain ridge	Trap in place Aug 2023* – August 2024, photo capture on 25.08.2023 at 01:10
J-05	DNA scatology	1 scat	3930	Saddle ridge	DNA collected on 10.08.2024
Q-08	DNA scatology	1 scat	4093	Rocky ground	DNA collected on 12.08.2024
M-13	DNA scatology	1 scat	3703	Mountain ridge	DNA collected on 15.08.2024
L-13	DNA scatology	1 scat	3823	Mountain ridge	DNA collected on 15.08.2024
Q-08	Track	1 track	3800	Muddy slope	Track detected on 12.08.2024. Correct track identification is difficult and error-prone and should be treated with caution.

*camera traps placed by reconnaissance expedition in 2023 and left *in situ*.

Figure 2.3a. Snow leopard detection in cells. CT = camera trap, SC = scat, TR = track.

Of the 15 scat samples collected by the expedition, four turned out to be from snow leopard (Table 2.3a), the rest were from Mongolian wolf (Appendix II). One track found in one cell was thought to be of snow leopard. However, correct track identification is difficult and error-prone and should be treated with caution.

Eighteen photos of snow leopard were captured by four camera traps in four cells, representing 1.2% of all photographed wild animals. Twelve pictures were taken in August and September 2023 (by camera traps that had been left in the field by a reconnaissance expedition in 2023), the remaining six photos were taken in August 2024. Photos were taken at night (capture at 01:10 by camera trap BE20, 03:42 by BE07 and 03:56 by BE06), morning (07:12 by BE06) and evening (21:04 by BE07).

Individual identification of snow leopards through camera trap pictures is possible by the size and location of spots on the fur, especially on the paws, sides, the upper surface of the tail, as well as the forehead (Blomquist et al. 1980). All camera trap photos were processed and analysed, yielding identification of individuals in some cases (Figure 2.3b-g).

Figure 2.3b. Visual analysis of snow leopard markings, leading to the identification of individual animals.
Photos of camera trap BE35 (C-1 and C-2) captured the same animal in the same sequence.

The long fur marking at the base of the tail and spine of photos A and B show significant differences: the marking in photo A is wide and intermittent; in photo B, the shape is thin and long. Spots on the right foreleg in pictures B and C are similar. However, three spots in C are located close to the paw. There are clear differences on the left foreleg between photos B and C. In B, three lines of spots are visible, in C-2 there are four lines. Spot comparison is difficult between A and C. However, the clearly differing body size is a strong indication of two different individuals, especially because there is little time between the photos to allow for a change in body size and composition.

Figure 2.3c. Camera trap BE-06 recording snow leopard.

Figure 2.3d. Camera trap BE-35 recording snow leopard.

Figure 2.3e. Camera trap BE-07 recording snow leopard.

Figure 2.3f. Camera trap BE-06 recording snow leopard. The tail of a snow leopard is visible on the left edge.

Figure 2.3g. Camera trap BE-20 recording snow leopard. A snow leopard is visible on the right edge.

Ibex *Capra sibirica*

Ibex was recorded in 34 cells (Table 2.3b, Figure 2.3h). Camera trap images (Figures 2.3i-l) were taken during the day, indicating a diurnal lifestyle. The skulls found near a farm indicate poaching activities.

Table 2.3b. Ibex detection records during the expedition.

Cell number	Detection method	Detection result
I-12	Sign	Scat
I-13	Sign	Scat
J-06	Sign	Track
J-07	Sign	Track
J-07	Camera trap BE-13	9 images
J-07	Camera trap BE-16	2 images
J-08	Camera trap BE-14	7 images
J-13	Direct sighting	5 images
K-07	Sign	Scat
K-09	Direct sighting	6 individuals
L-09	Camera trap BE-18	23 individuals (12 female, 11 young)
L-10	Remains found	Skull
L-12	Direct sighting	<38 individuals (8 male, <30 young with mothers)
L-12	Direct sighting	<5 individuals
L-13	Signs	Track, scat
L-16	Remains found	Skull near farm at entrance of Kalcha Valley
M-14	Sign	Scat
M-21	Remains found	Skull near farm at entrance of Kalcha Valley
N-10	Camera trap BE-20	5 individuals
N-11	Sign	Bones
N-12	Signs	Track, scat
O-04	Sign	Scat
O-09	Sign	Track
O-11	Remains found	Horn
O-13	Camera trap BE-07	35 individuals
O-14	Remains found	Skull near farm at entrance of Kalcha Valley
O-15	Sign	Scat
O-16	Remains found	Skull near farm at entrance of Kalcha Valley, 3 individuals
P-09	Camera trap BE-15	3 individuals
P-09	Camera trap BE-35	37 individuals.
P-10	Camera trap BE-19	3 individuals (1 male, 2 female)
P-11	Signs	Track, scat
P-14	Camera trap BE-23	10 individuals (8 male, 1 female, 1 young)
P-16	Remains found	Horn
Q-8	Signs	Tracks in the mud, scat
Q-12	Direct sighting	6 individuals
R-12	Direct sighting	7 individuals
R-13	Direct sighting	7 individuals

Figure 2.3i. Ibex recorded by camera traps BE-07 / BE-13 / BE-14.

Figure 2.3j. Ibex recorded by camera traps BE-15 / BE-16 / BE-18.

Figure 2.3k. Ibex recorded by camera traps BE-19 / BE-20.

Figure 2.3l. Ibex recorded by camera traps BE-23 / BE-35.

Argali *Ovis ammon*

Argali was recorded in three cells, from remains and scats. Skulls of argali were found in cells K-16 and N-14 near a hut, strongly indicating poaching activities (Figure 2.3m). There were no direct sightings of argali.

Figure 2.3m. Argali detection in cells. SC = scat, SK = skull.

Marmot *Marmota baibacina*

Marmot was recorded in 97 cells (Figure 2.3n) by direct sighting, camera trap (Figure 2.3o), scat, call and burrows.

Legend

- Grid lines
- Rivers
- Surveyed cells
- Marmot
- Animal record type

Figure 2.3n. Marmot detection in cells.
 CT = camera trap, DS = direct sighting, SC = scat, SK = skull, BU = burrow, CL = call.

Bushnell

05-18-2024 10:40:56

Figure 2.3o. Marmot recorded by camera trap BE-35.

Tolai Hare *Lepus tolai*

Tolai hare was recorded in 16 cells by direct sighting, scat and burrows, and by camera trap BE-35 (Figure 2.3q) at night.

Legend

Figure 2.3p. Tolai hare detection in cells.
 CT = camera trap, DS = direct sighting, SC = scat, BU = burrow.

Figure 2.3q. Tolai hare recorded by camera trap BE-35.

Mongolian wolf *Canis lupus chanco*

Mongolian wolf was recorded in 13 cells from DNA scatology and camera traps (Figures 2.3s-t). Eleven scat samples, all from cells O-10 and P-08, were initially thought to be from snow leopard, but were confirmed to be from Mongolian wolf by DNA analysis.

Legend

Figure 2.3r. Mongolian wolf detection in cells. CT = camera trap, SC = scat.

Figure 2.3s. Mongolian wolf recorded by camera trap BE-06.

Figure 2.3t. Mongolian wolf recorded by camera trap BE-35 (first, second) and camera trap BE-23.

Fox Vulpes vulpes

Fox was recorded in two cells. Camera trapping recorded one fox at night (Figure 2.3v). Scat samples (unconfirmed by DNA analysis) were found in two cells.

Figure 2.3u. Fox detection in cells. CT = camera trap, SC = scat.

Bushnell

06-23-2024 22:22:32

Figure 2.3v. Fox recorded by camera trap BE-07.

Stone marten *Martes foina*

Stone marten was recorded in five cells, exclusively by camera traps (Figures 2.3x-y). All images were taken at night, indicating a nocturnal lifestyle.

Figure 2.3w. Stone marten detection in cells by CT = camera trap.

Figure 2.3x. Stone marten recorded by camera traps BE-06 / BE-07.

Figure 2.3y. Stone marten recorded by camera traps BE-16 / BE-19 / BE-35.

Steppe polecat *Mustela eversmanii*

Steppe polecat was recorded in two cells by direct sighting. Citizen scientists witnessed a steppe polecat preying on a marmot by biting its head off and dragging the carcass into a burrow (Figure 2.3aa and [video](#)).

Legend

Figure 2.3z. Steppe polecat detection in cells by DS = direct sighting.

Figure 2.3aa. Steppe polecat pictures taken by citizen scientists S. Issar (top) and S. Mannweiler (bottom). In the top picture (and the [video](#)), the bloodied carcass of marmot prey can be seen.

Badger *Meles leucurus*

Badger was recorded in 25 cells, mostly from scats.

Figure 2.3ab. Badger detection in cells by DS = direct sighting, SC = scat, BU = burrow.

It should be noted that the burrow of a badger is similar in size to that of marmots, but differs in excrement found in front of the burrow. Badger excrement is dark in colour and contains insect remains (mainly beetles).

Weasel *Mustela nivalis*

Weasel was recorded in four cells, by direct sighting and scat (Figure 2.3ac).

Figure 2.3ac. Weasel detection in cells by DS = direct sighting and SC = scat.

Moles *Talpida* sp.

Moles were recorded in 29 cells from burrows, except for two cells in which scats (unconfirmed by DNA analysis) were found.

Legend

Figure 2.3ad. Mole detection in cells by BU = burrow and SC = scat.

Rodents

Rodents were recorded in 24 cells, mainly by burrows, except for direct sightings in two cells and scats in six cells. Rodents are ubiquitous around human settlements and regularly translocated inadvertently to highland areas by humans (Tarasov 1961).

Legend

Figure 2.3ae. Rodent detection in cells by BU = burrow, DS = direct sighting and SC = scat.

Shepherd interviews & community engagement

Citizen scientists and staff interviewed 16 shepherds, 15 in Burkhan valley and one in Archaly valley (Figure 2.3af & ag), using a [standardised interview datasheet](#). The expedition also engaged with the local communities during two traditional shepherd celebrations with [Kok-Boru \(dead goat\) games](#). During these gatherings, the expedition presented its mission to those present and talked about the importance of nature conservation for livelihoods based on livestock grazing. The expedition also invited the local community to base camp to talk about the same topics (Figure 2.3ah). This happened twice with approximately 150 people attending each time. Finally, the expedition routinely collected rubbish whilst out on fieldwork.

Figures Tables 2.3c & d show the results of the interviews.

Figure 2.3af. Location of 16 shepherd interviews, 15 of them in Burkhan valley, one in Archaly valley.

Figure 2.3ag. After an interview with a local shepherd.

Figure 2.3ah. The expedition scientist (left with microphone) engaging with the local community at base camp.

Table 2.3c. Interview results (over multiple pages). NAG = no answer given, SL = snow leopard, KY = Kyrgyzstan.

Number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
Name	Maksat	Ernis	Erlan	Kustarbek	-	Kereksiz	-	Asylbek	Suyunbai	Gulnur	-	Maya	Nurlan	Diana	Cholpon	Nurbek
Age	45	29	40	51	-	58	65	57	≈50-60	≈40-50	≈40	-	45	-	45	62
Gender	Male	Male	Male	Male	Male	Male	Male	Male	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Female	Male
Place of birth	Bokon-baev	Bokon-baev	Bokon-baev	Bokon-baev	Bokon-baev	Tortkul	Tortkul	Tortkul	Bokon-baev	Bokon-baev	Bokon-baev	Zhekendy	-	Zhekendy	Ton region	Bokon-baev
Place of residence	Bokon-baev	Bokon-baev	Bokon-baev	Bokon-baev	Bokon-baev	Tortkul	Tortkul	Tortkul	Bokon-baev	Bokon-baev	Bokon-baev	Bokon-baev	Bokon-baev	Bokon-baev	Temir-Kanat	Bokon-baev
Occupation	Shepherd	Shepherd	Shepherd	Shepherd	Shepherd	Shepherd	Shepherd	Shepherd	Shepherd	Shepherd	Shepherd	Shepherd	Shepherd	Herder	Shepherd	Shepherd
Livestock herded	1k sheep 40 cow 30 horse	1.3k sheep 250 horse 200 cow	1k sheep 10 horse 1 donkey	NAG	1.3k sheep 20 cow	1k sheep 200 cow 40 horse	1k sheep 200 cow 200 horse	NAG	800 sheep 20 horse 12 cow	1k sheep 70 horse	1k sheep	NAG	NAG	NAG	1k sheep 50 cow 20 goat 10 horse 2 donkey	300+ yak 20 cow 5 horse
Herd every year?	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
When?	May-Oct	May-Oct	May-Oct	May-Oct	May-Oct	May-Oct	May-Oct	May-Oct	May-Oct	May-Oct	May-Oct	May-Oct	May-Oct	May-Sep	Jun-Aug	All year
Herding with	Family	Family	Family	Alone	Family	Family	Family	Family	Family, workers	Family	Family	Family	Family	Husband	Family	Family
Typical day	Herding Milking	Herding Dairy production	Herding Milking	Herding Dairy production	Herding Dairy production	Herding Milking	Herding	Herding Milking Meeting people	Herding Dairy production (kurut)	Herding Dairy production (kurut) Looking after son	Herding	Dairy production	Herding Dairy production Meat production	Milking Dairy production	Herding Dairy production	Herding
Seen SL?	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
Details of sighting or sign	NAG	NAG	Saw SL kill ibex in 2021	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	Horse attack in Bordu gorge
SL hearsay	Attacked livestock between Burkhan &Jyluu-Suu valleys	No	NAG	No	NAG	Other people have seen SL	Heard that SL attack livestock	Horse attack in 2023 in Akkor- umtor gorge	NAG	Other people have seen SL	Other people have seen SL, horse attack in 2020/21	NAG	NAG	NAG	No	NAG
SL impact	Beneficial	Neither	Detri- mental	Neither	Neither	Beneficial	Detri- mental	Beneficial in low numbers, detrimental if more	Neither	Neither	Neither	Beneficial	NAG	NAG	Neither	Beneficial
Good or bad for KY	Good	Good	Good	Good	Good	Good	Good	Good	Good	NAG	Good	Good	NAG	NAG	Neutral	Good

Table 2.3c. Interview results (continued). NAG = no answer given, SL = snow leopard, KY = Kyrgyzstan.

Number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	
Name	Maksat	Ernis	Erlan	Kustarbek	-	Kereksiz	-	Asylbek	Suyunbai	Gulnur	-	Maya	Nurlan	Diana	Cholpon	Nurbek	
<i>Feelings about SL</i>	Positive and very proud	Neither	No interests or opinion	NAG	NAG	In favour	Good they exist, bad if they attack livestock	Positive	Positive if few, but wary of livestock attacks if more	Positive if few, but wary of livestock attacks if more	Positive if few, but wary of livestock attacks if more	Positive	SL not a problem, wolves are	Not bothered by SL in summer	Positive	Positive, beautiful animal	
<i>Like SL?</i>	Like	Neither	Indifferent – SL should not harm livestock	Like	Like	Like	Neither	Like	Like	Neither	NAG	Neither	Neither	Neither	Like	Like	
<i>SL attack people?</i>	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	NAG	NAG	Don't know	Don't know	Don't know	No	No	No	
<i>What provokes attack?</i>	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	Don't know	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	
<i>SL attacks frequent where there are people?</i>	No	NAG	Yes	NAG	NAG	Don't know	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	Haven't heard about it
<i>How many SL in KGS</i>	Don't know	Don't know	Don't know	Don't know	Don't know	Don't know	Don't know	Don't know	Don't know	NAG	Don't know	NAG	NAG	NAG	200	Don't know	
<i>Should SL be protected in KGS</i>	Yes	Yes	Don't know	No	NAG	Yes	Yes	Yes	Don't know	NAG	Yes	NAG	NAG	NAG	Yes	Yes	
<i>Additional comments on SL</i>	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	SL protection only on paper, without action	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	Good SL protection with heavy fines and jail terms exists
<i>Do SL affect game numbers?</i>	No	They prey on ibex	Don't know	NAG	NAG	Don't know	Yes	Don't know	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	Yes
<i>How so or why not</i>	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	SL kill only when hungry	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	SL prey on wild animals
<i>Do SL affect small animal numbers?</i>	No	NAG	Don't know	No	No	Don't know	Don't know	Don't know	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	No	

Table 2.3c. Interview results (continued). NAG = no answer given, SL = snow leopard, KY = Kyrgyzstan.

Number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16		
Name	Maksat	Ernis	Erlan	Kustarbek	-	Kereksiz	-	Asylbek	Suyunbai	Gulnur	-	Maya	Nurlan	Diana	Cholpon	Nurbek		
<i>How so or why not?</i>	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	SL prey on marmots, but there are many	
<i>Do SL prey on livestock?</i>	No	Yes	No	NAG	NAG	Yes	Yes	Yes	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	Yes	No	
<i>How so or why not?</i>	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	SL attack livestock near Ysyk-Kol	SL attack livestock near	SL attack livestock in Ton region	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	SL attacked horse many years ago
<i>SL attracting more tourists is..?</i>	Good	Good	Good	Good	Good	Good	Good	Good	NAG	Don't know	Good	NAG	Good	NAG	Don't know	Good	Good	
<i>Interested in helping expedition?</i>	No (but ended up being very helpful)	Yes	Yes	NAG	NAG	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes, needs more details	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
<i>How? What can you provide?</i>	No time, because he is very busy	Kymyz Kurut Meat	Handicrafts	NAG	NAG	Kymyz Meat	Meat Dairy products	Meat Handicrafts	Yurt Kymyz Kurut Horse rental	NAG	Meat Horse rental	Honey Dairy products	Meat Dairy products	Bread Dairy products	Milk	Food Advice Guiding Horse rental Facilities		
<i>Interested in coming to base for info evening?</i>	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	Yes	
<i>Anything else</i>	Wolves bigger danger to livestock and kill livestock for fun. Why is conservation only for SL? SL drinks blood.	In 2006 he heard from another shepherd that he saw a SL gave birth to a cub.	No interest. SL is just one of many wildlife in KY.	NAG	NAG	SL are beauty of nature and we should protect them.	-	Locals should be more involved in nature conservation process as it's their land.	SL not an issue in summer	SL not relevant in her daily life. Curious about foreigners visiting this remote place.	SL numbers should increase. Supports efforts of expedition.	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	NAG	Especially interested in location of camera traps.	

Table 2.3d. Summary of interview results.

Age	29-65, average 49
Gender	12 (75%) male, 4 (25%) female
Occupation	All but one interviewee specified “shepherd”, only one “herder”. The difference is semantic. It is noteworthy that all of them are employed by a livestock owner to herd livestock that is not their own. Their typical day consists of herding and dairy production, which does not appear to be tied to gender.
Livestock herded	The mainstay is large flocks of sheep, supplemented mainly by cow and horse and occasionally by goat and donkey. There was only one yak herder who did not have sheep. It is important to note that there is an incentive to understate the size of flocks to save on taxes. This is likely to have been the case here too, corroborated by visual spot checks.
Herding practices	Most herders work together with their families in the study site every year between May and October.
Snow leopard knowledge and experience	Only one interviewee claimed (credibly) to have seen a snow leopard. One claims to have seen a snow leopard kill an ibex, but the credibility of this claim is doubtful. Three interviewees (19%) claimed that people they know have seen snow leopard. Four interviewees (25%) had heard of snow leopard attacking livestock. Only one interviewee made a very good guess that there are 200 snow leopards in Kyrgyzstan (official estimates vary between 150 and 500), the rest did not know or did not answer.
Snow leopard impact	The majority (n=9 [56%]) believe that snow leopard has no impact on them or their livelihoods, or they had no opinion on this. Five (31%) believe that snow leopard has a beneficial impact and only three (18%) cited a detrimental impact. The most interesting answers were that snow leopard in low numbers are beneficial, but detrimental in high numbers. This is corroborated by the answers about how people feel about snow leopard. The majority (n=11 [69%]) thought that there is no danger to people from snow leopard attacks, the rest did not know or did not give an answer. There was also little concern about game or small animal impact through snow leopard predation, but livestock impact was a concern for five interviewees (32%).
Feelings towards snow leopard	75% (n=12) believe that snow leopard is good for Kyrgyzstan and there was some clear pride expressed for this emblematic animal. 50% (n=8) thought that snow leopard should be protected in Kyrgyzstan. However, it is also clear that there is a very clear line for this pride and support to end when the animal attacks livestock. Only one shepherd declared that he was ready to sacrifice livestock for the sake of snow leopards.
Snow leopard and tourism / the expedition	There is a clear interest in alternative sources of income through snow leopard presence. 75% (n=12) believe that snow leopard attracting tourism was a good thing. 81% (n=13) were interested in helping the expedition, mainly by providing food (11 [69%]) and also through handicrafts (n=1 [6%]) and services such as horse rental, facilities and guiding (n=3 [19%]). The expedition ended up utilising all these offer types. Curiously the person (Maksat / interviewee #1) most explicit about not having time to help the expedition, ended up providing the most help. A sizeable minority (n=7 [44%]) wanted to find out more about the expedition’s work by attending an information evening at base camp.
Other comments	Wolves appear to be considered a much bigger problem than snow leopard and are universally loathed (and persecuted, with state bounties paid for kills). It is interesting to note that one interviewee thought that snow leopard are only protected on paper with no meaningful action, whereas another interviewee thought the opposite: that there is good protection with fines and jail terms in place. One interviewee was concerned that conservation activity was done by foreigners instead of the local people who own the land.

2.4. Discussion

Wildlife dataset

When expeditions started in 2003, a streamlined version of a method called SLIMS (Snow Leopard Information Management System) (Jackson and Hunter 1996) was used. This method records rates of snow leopard sign (scats, pugmarks, scent mark, scrape and claw rake) per transect. The system, if correctly employed, is still valuable as a supplementary dataset (see McCarthy et al. 2008, Lukarevsky et al. 2019, 2020) and has been used successfully to provide rates per transected area elsewhere in previous Biosphere Expeditions studies (Mazzolli 2009).

After publication of Mazzolli & Hammer (2013), more advanced research tools were added to the expedition toolkit, such as camera traps, the use of grids in study design and data analysis and, most recently, DNA scatology.

Results from previous expeditions have recorded snow leopards, scoring from 0 to 5 counts and/or cells annually, mostly by tracks, sighting, and more recently also by camera trap (since 2018) and DNA scatology (since 2024). The same methods were applied to record other species of interest, all to identify distributional range as an alternative variable to abundance, which in turn is informative of habitat quality.

Interviews and community engagement

The shepherds of Burkhan and Archaly valleys are engaged in animal husbandry on an ongoing basis and take their livestock (mainly very large herds of sheep measuring in their thousands) out on pasture from May to October every year. According to the anti-poaching unit Grupa Bars, and in contrast to previous sites, the education level of herders at the current study site is high. Herders live in families and pass on their skills from one generation to the next, but they do not own the land and livestock, or only 10-15% of the livestock. Instead, the land is owned by pasture committees and the majority of livestock by large livestock owners who employ the herders and exact compensation from them for heads of livestock lost.

As such, it is not surprising that the interviews showed that snow leopard presence is tolerated by local shepherds as long as it does not impact livestock through predation. Wolves are considered a much bigger problem and are universally loathed and persecuted, with bounties paid by the state for each wolf killed. By contrast, the snow leopard is often admired for its beauty and emblematic quality and a source of pride for some. The impact of snow leopard presence on the daily lives of the herders is negligible.

There was significant interest in alternative means of income through tourism, in this case the expedition. A side effect welcomed by the community was income generation when shepherd families sold their products (food, handicraft and services) to citizen scientists or the expedition or hosted the expedition team. For example, citizen scientists purchased wool handicrafts from Maksat Mukanbetov who in turn ordered a new batch of souvenirs from his relatives from the village of Bokonbayev for the next group of citizen scientists. The expedition also purchased bread, butter and other dairy products from the community.

The expedition was also invited to the dwellings of Maksat Mukanbetov and Erlan Saliev for a traditional meal and paid for the food and drink served. Other shepherds expressed their interest in doing this for future expedition groups.

In general, we believe that interviewees gave accurate answers to most questions. For tax reasons, they commonly understated the size of their herds, but we have no reason to believe their answers were disingenuous otherwise.

However, a common undercurrent was poaching. There were no direct questions asked about this, but we believe that most herders engage in poaching, indeed one interviewee admitted to this openly. Ibex meat, for example, is considered a healthy delicacy, and the Grupa Bars stated that a common belief amongst herders is that poaching is their right as guardians of the land. Interviewees showed intense interest in the number and location of the expedition camera traps during interviews and often this was one of the first questions that was asked. We believe this is for fear of exposing poaching activities. We believe the behaviour during interviews and other information gathered corroborates significant poaching activities by herders, concentrating on ungulate game animals.

All this results in a clear juxtaposition of widespread support for snow leopard presence (as long as this does not result in livestock predation) and conservation, and suspicion towards the expedition, especially its camera-trapping activities, and in a few cases also the involvement of foreigners in conserving native animals and lands of Kyrgyzstan.

Finally, it emerged from the interviews and other conversations during the expedition that shepherds are worried about drought issues, such as the decrease of water levels in rivers and the spread of the invasive [Caragana frutex](#) plant across pasture land.

Snow leopard prey and its effects on snow leopard distribution

Records so far indicate that marmot and ibex are the most common prey of the snow leopard, followed by argali, hare and snowcock. Argali has been recorded at decreasing rates at all study sites since expeditions began. Of all remaining relevant large mammals present at the study sites, wolf is most frequently recorded, whereas lynx, wild boar, red deer, musk deer, wolverine and bear are rarely recorded. Previous expeditions also published surveys on birds, butterflies, petroglyphs and plants, and modelled habitat quality using GIS (see [here](#) for a full list of expedition reports and publications arising out of expedition work).

The literature supports the observed rareness of argali found by all previous expeditions except the first two expeditions in 2003 and 2004 to the Altai. This is because the preferred habitat of argali is also very suitable for livestock grazing, which is one of the major drivers of habitat degradation and displacement (UNEP 2024). It follows that argali should indeed be rare, because their habitat is, with few exceptions, taken by livestock alongside herders that will not hesitate to hunt argali for meat. The argali is also a prized hunting trophy because of the shape and size of its horns. Zuther et al. (2024) corroborate this by stating that only in exceptional circumstances and 'in the absence of poaching and where livestock is free-ranging or herded without dogs, argali can become habituated to people and domestic animals and even share pastures with them'. In highly disturbed areas such as the study site, however, argali are likely to disappear and ibex numbers drop (Khanyari et al. 2021).

Fluctuations of argali signs during expeditions, supported by information from the literature (e.g. Callaghan et al. 2024), suggests that argali has the characteristics (vulnerability to environmental and anthropogenic conditions, and easiness of recording when present) to be an excellent indicator species for snow leopard habitat.

However, argali records were not always low during expeditions: In 2003 and 2004 the expeditions to the Talduair massif in the Chikhachev Ridge group of the Altai mountains recorded higher records of argali than ibex. This changed from 2004 to 2008, when there was a three-fold drop in the argali sign rate and ibex sign rates became more frequent (Tytar & Hammer 2009). This trend continued as argali sign rate dropped from 38% of all transects in 2009 to 25% in 2010 and then to 18% in 2011.

Ibex, on the other hand, seems to be more resilient than argali, due to their adaptation to higher peaks, where disturbances are significantly fewer. Prior expeditions to both the Altai and the Tien Shan have shown ibex to be confined to high altitudes. Realising that ibex was the most abundant ungulate prey species for snow leopards in the surveyed areas, Tytar et al. (2019) modelled snow leopard-preferred habitats as a function of ibex distribution. The authors inferred that leopards would be distributed where ibex were present. The spatial data was then used to direct subsequent expedition sampling efforts. Scientists and readers alike must bear in mind, though, that those associations were found in areas where the grazing valleys are under high human pressure. Distribution of leopards may, no doubt, be associated with the highest peaks under those circumstances.

Jumabay-Uulu et al. (2014), on the other hand, reported that argali was the most important prey species of snow leopards (and wolves) where herders and their livestock were absent, namely in the Sarychat-Ertash Reserve in Kyrgyzstan, where argali is able to thrive, resulting in a shift of ecological patterns to a more low-human-impact original and natural state.

Based on all this, we argue that current livestock and grazing pressures are responsible for reduced argali numbers, and also for confinement of leopards to higher altitudes. Despite the snow leopard's undeniable adaptations to high mountain habitats, it is flexible enough to explore lower altitudes in search of prey. For example, snow leopards were found at 1,500–2,000 m in the Gobi Desert by Janečka et al. (2011). One individual in Nepal was even recorded below 200 m (Chetri et al. 2024). This means that snow leopards are able to at least cross low altitude areas between mountain ranges, thereby ensuring gene flow amongst populations. The occupation of lower altitudes by settlements, herders and their livestock, therefore, is likely to be a significant barrier to genetic exchange.

Status of and threats to the snow leopard

Based on the results presented here, especially the identification of individuals via camera trap photos, we estimate that at least two, perhaps three, snow leopards populate the Burkhan and Archaly valleys. This fits well with Johansson et al. (2016), who quote male snow leopard home range as 220 sq km and female snow leopard home range as 130 sq km. The expedition study site is around 1000 sq km, of which 536 sq km were sampled. The study site contains about 580 sq km of high mountain habitat suitable for snow leopard, not all of which was sampled, but all snow leopard sign that was found by the expedition was detected

in such habitat (Figure 2.3a). Two, perhaps three, snow leopards of unknown sex therefore seems a reasonable estimate. Whether they are transient or resident is unknown and requires further study. We aim to do this in 2025 by conducting DNA analyses down to individual level, rather than just species level as in 2024, and by setting up camera trap stations where animals are photographed from two sides to increase the chances of identification of individuals through spot coat patterns from two sides.

The Tien Shan is a mountain range that connects biodiversity of different mountain ranges in Central Asia. Snow leopard gene flow through the Tien Shan is poorly understood, with current data new and preliminary: While Cancellare et al. (2024) report a lack of strong snow leopard phylogeographic structure across a large distributional range, Wang et al. (2024) suggest the existence of three distinct groups.

Livestock depredation and subsequent retaliatory killings by herders is also a concern for snow leopard survival, although it does not seem to be a significant problem in the study site, where herders are broadly in favour of snow leopard presence as long as they do not prey on livestock, which they do not appear to in the study site. Herders mostly blame the wolf for livestock losses, which is corroborated by our interview findings, but snow leopards are also known to prey on domestic animals (e.g. Suryawashi et al. 2017, Chetri et al. 2019).

A strategy to reduce livestock depredation suggested in the literature is to have argali amongst livestock to buffer against snow leopard attacks. This would be an interesting experiment to be implemented. If successful, herders would then have every reason not to shoot argali or even other leopard prey species. Current literature is still inconclusive regarding the increase of wild prey to minimise livestock losses. There are indications that increased wild prey and a hunting ban of argali does not decrease livestock depredation (Namgail et al. 2009, Suryawanshi et al. 2017), whereas there is also indication that it is effective: studies in India and Mongolia have shown that snow leopard prefer wild ungulates over livestock, even when the latter was much more abundant than the former (Johansson et al. 2016, Suryawanshi et al. 2017, Qi Lu et al. 2021). Spitsyn et al. (2021) recorded that the presence of argali put an end to livestock attack by wolves (Callaghan et al. 2024).

Observations made by the current expedition suggest that the damage caused to vegetation by grazing in the study area is not catastrophic. However, it should be noted that in high-altitude climatic conditions, recovery from human and livestock impact can be very slow.

The expedition also found that ibex and argali ascend to the mountain ridges in summer, where snow leopards follow them, and were photographed by the expedition in August and September between 3718 and 3928 m altitude. It will be interesting to know what happens in winter at lower altitudes, as ungulates descend as winter starts. For this reason, the expedition left one camera trap in place at 3112 m altitude. In this context it is interesting to note that twelve of the 18 expedition snow leopard photos were taken in August/September 2023, by cameras trap left by a reconnaissance expedition in the summer of 2023. Another six photos of a single individual passing a camera trap were taken in August 2024, by a camera also placed in 2023. As such it would make sense to leave more camera traps in place between expeditions in future, either in remote locations that are unlikely to be found by local herders, who would then more than likely remove the camera traps, or by finding herders that are willing to protect and maintain camera traps between expedition periods.

In summary, the expedition identified the following threats (in order of importance) to snow leopard survival in the study area:

1. We believe poaching of snow leopard prey species, mainly for meat, is rife within the study site. One result of this is the extreme rarity or local extinction of argali. The expedition also found clear evidence of illegal hunting at the entrance of Kalcha Valley, where skulls of argali were found in cells K-16 and N-14, in the vicinity of a hunting hut. The management plan for the development of Sarychat-Eertash Nature Reserve also lists prey poaching as a threat. Hunting tours for foreign hunters are conducted in Kyrgyzstan, mainly for males of the argali and the Siberian ibex with their impressive horns. The sale of hunting permits contributes about half a million dollars a year to the country's treasury (NSLEP Kyrgyzstan), but this money does not make any contribution to the development of the natural reserve, although the hunting targets live and breeding animals in the reserve. This is another aspect of this significant problem, albeit in the wider vicinity.

2. Excessive, unregulated overgrazing, leading to pasture degradation and the competitive displacement of wild ungulate snow leopard prey species, whose numbers have dramatically decreased, is another serious concern. Extensive overgrazing is incompatible with the limited environmental pressures that highly vulnerable mountain ecosystems can withstand (Shukurov 1991). High livestock numbers lead to overgrazing, splash erosion and topsoil compaction. Fifteen percent of the upper basin of the Naryn River is prone to this, seven percent is at high risk and in three percent there is an extremely high amount of soil erosion, which varies between 0 to $0.018\text{t ha}^{-1}\text{ yr}^{-1}$ (Duulatov et al. 2023). Beside natural causes (topography, wind), overgrazing – as observed throughout the expedition – is enhancing soil erosion. Between the ridges of Jetim-Bel and Burkhan rivers, the expedition noted 44 temporary shepherd structures (Figure 2.3af), each of them holding at least one thousand sheep, as well as two to five herds of horses and cows. This is simply too much and to make matters worse, the growing demand for meat and other livestock products leads to even more interest in grazing and an increase in the number of livestock. In Burkhan valley, average vegetation height was 5-7 cm. In Archaly valley, on the other hand, where significantly less livestock was observed, the vegetation was noticeably lusher, with an average height of 25-30 cm. Vegetation degradation leads to splash erosion of soil cover and a runaway degradation of general habitat, which ultimately threatens snow leopard survival.

3. The wolf is persecuted throughout the countries of the former Soviet Union. Snow leopards can be caught in traps set for wolf. In addition, herding dogs may detect snow leopards, which may lead to them getting killed. At the very least, the presence of dogs adds a significant amount of stress for snow leopards.

4. The development of the area for mining is another significant threat. The open-pit Kumtor gold mine located 95 km to the east of the study site is one of the highest-altitude large enterprises in the world. Recently the Kyrgyz government announced plans for iron mining in the Jetim mountain range and the construction of highways between Kyrgyzstan and China via Bedel pass. Those economic activities will lead to the destruction and fragmentation of snow leopard habitat.

5. Climate change: As long as natural ecosystems retain a composition and structure close to their original state, they can respond flexibly to the heterogeneity of the mountain environment and climate fluctuations. According to forecasts by Kyrgyz climatologists, the average annual temperature in the range of 2.5-3.0°C and an increase in annual precipitation by 10-15% are expected in the republic by 2100 compared to their values in 1961-1990. (NSLEP Kyrgyzstan). Climate change manifests itself, first of all, in changes in the environmental conditions familiar to living species. Many animal species have natural adaptive capabilities developed in the course of evolution to migrate to areas with more favourable conditions. Thus, if the general environmental conditions change due to climate change, the most likely change will be a change in the territorial distribution of species, a shift in the altitude zone of the distribution of species up the slopes and a decrease in the number of the most vulnerable species, which include rare and endemic ones such as the snow leopard (Balbakova et al. 2016).

6. The Kyrgyz Republic is strengthening its state borders, which in many cases run through the mountainous habitats of the snow leopard. The increase in the number of border posts and the number of employees at the borders are likely to increase poaching activities. Also, in some areas border reinforcements include barbed wire fences, which prevent dispersal of wildlife, including the snow leopard.

7. Poaching for fur and by illegal hunting, as well as retaliatory killings, is always a threat for snow leopards, but the problem does not appear acute in the study site.

8. Unregulated tourism (cycling, rafting and horse riding) may become a problem in the future, but does not appear to be one now.

Overall conclusions

The number of two, perhaps three, snow leopards in the study area comprising 580 sq km of suitable high mountain habitat fits well with known home range sizes as described by Johansson et al. (2016). We will seek to corroborate this finding in 2025 by including scat DNA analysis down to individual level and by setting up camera trap stations where animals are photographed from two sides to increase the chances of identification of individuals through spot coat patterns from two sides.

It is clear that the Burkhan and Archaly valleys are prime snow leopard monitoring terrain as the area is relatively untouched by development, even though it is overgrazed and heavily poached for game ungulates. We believe that the area also serves as a migration corridor between Central and Inner Tien Shan, because all camera trap photos taken and all scats found were on the ridges of the Uch-Emchek and Jetim-Bel mountain ranges.

Just like in many other snow leopard areas around the world, controlling rampant poaching and overgrazing is key to snow leopard conservation. The power of such control mechanisms is demonstrated by Sarychat-Eertash Nature Reserve, where a healthy prey base of argali, ibex and marmot exists. As a result, snow leopard numbers began to recover from one in 1997 up to around 20 by 2021 (Suyundukov & Choduraev 2022). We believe that if control mechanisms of the two main threats to snow leopard – poaching and overgrazing – were introduced in the Burkhan and Archaly valleys, then the area could become a significant snow leopard stronghold.

Tasks for the next expedition

1. Extend the surveys up to Terskey Ala-Too and Jetim mountain ranges.
2. Continue research and corroborate findings to make conservation recommendations.
3. Include DNA analysis of scat down to individual level into the study to elucidate snow leopard numbers in the study site.
4. Set up camera trap stations where animals are photographed from two sides to increase the chances of identification of individuals through spot coat patterns from two sides.
5. Improve cooperation with local communities and find people to maintain camera traps between expeditions.

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Appendix I: Overview of camera trap results. See also Appendix IV for other species of interest photographed.

No.	Cell	Species recorded	Placed on	Removed on	Total pictures taken	Wild animals	Live-stock	Snow leopard
BE06	L-12	Snow leopard, Stone marten, Wolf	09.08.2023	15.07.2024	33	13	-	3
BE07	O-13	Himalayan snowcock, Ibex, Stone marten, Yellow-billed chough, Fox, Snow leopard	12.08.2023	10.08.2024	435	339	-	6
BE08	O-01	Ibex	17.08.2023	09.08.2024	3784	49	-	-
BE09	P-10	-	03.08.2023	15.07.2024	208	-	-	-
BE13	J-07	Himalayan snowcock, Stone marten, Marmot, Ibex	16.08.2023	14.08.2024	157	83	-	-
BE14	J-08	Himalayan snowcock, Ibex	14.08.2023	19.07.2024	54	54	-	-
BE15	P-09	Horse, Ibex, Tolai hare	11.08.2023	11.07.2024	164	53	18	-
BE16	J-07	Ibex, Rock sparrow, Stone marten	28.07.2023	19.07.2024	2893	207	-	-
BE17	K-14	Not achieved	14.08.2023					
BE18	L-09	Himalayan snowcock, Ibex	10.08.2023	13.07.2024	105	99	-	-
BE19	P-10	Rock sparrow, Yellow-billed chough, Ibex, Stone marten, Himalayan snowcock, Mouse	11.08.2023	15.07.2024	5919	104	-	-
BE20	P-14	Yellow-billed chough	12.08.2023	24.07.2024	4155	9	-	3
BE20	O-10	Ibex	02.08.2024	10.08.2024	400	30	-	-
BE23	P-14	Ibex	12.08.2023	24.07.2024	7455			
BE24	J-08	-	14.08.2023	19.07.2024	4587	-	-	-
BE25	O-13	Stolen	12.08.2023					
BE30	L-12	-	09.08.2023	15.07.2024	352	-	-	-
BE34	O-13	Himalayan snowcock, Yellow-billed chough, Shikra, Stone marten	17.08.2023	10.08.2024	3139	55	-	-
BE35	P-09	Stone marten, Ibex, Himalayan snowcock, Snow leopard, Tolai hare, Marmot, White-winged snowfinch, Wolf	11.08.2023	11.07.2024	687	500	-	3

Appendix II: Summary of DNA samples collected

No.	Date	Cell	Species	Sample type
1	19.07.2024	O-10	Wolf	Scat
2	19.07.2024	O-10	Wolf	Scat
3	19.07.2024	O-10	Wolf	Scat
4	19.07.2024	O-10	Wolf	Scat
5	19.07.2024	O-10	Wolf	Scat
6	07.08.2024	K-08	Wolf	Scat
7	07.08.2024	K-08	Wolf	Scat
8	07.08.2024	K-08	Wolf	Scat
9	08.08.2024	P-08	Wolf	Scat
10	10.08.2024	J-05	Snow leopard	Scat
11	12.08.2024	R-08	Wolf	Scat
12	12.08.2024	Q-08	Snow leopard	Scat
13	14.08.2024	L-12	Wolf	Scat
14	15.08.2024	M-13	Snow leopard	Scat
15	15.08.2024	L-13	Snow leopard	Scat

Appendix III: List of birds recorded by the expedition

This list is mainly a result of citizen scientists with an affinity for birding recording the species they encountered.

Common name	Scientific name	Sighting	Camera trap
Black Kite	<i>Milvus migrans</i>	✓	
Brown Accentor	<i>Prunella fulvescens</i>	✓	
Chinese Pond Heron	<i>Ardeola bacchus</i>	✓	
Citrine Wagtail	<i>Motacilla citreola</i>	✓	
Common Buzzard	<i>Buteo buteo</i>	✓	
Common Kestrel	<i>Falco tinnunculus</i>	✓	
Common Redshank	<i>Tringa totanus</i>	✓	
Common Rock Thrush	<i>Monticola saxatilis</i>	✓	
Common Rose Finch	<i>Carpodacus erythrinus</i>	✓	
Common Sandpiper	<i>Actitis hypoleucos</i>	✓	
Crow	<i>Corvus spp.</i>	✓	
Eurasian Hoopoe	<i>Upupa epops</i>	✓	
Golden Eagle	<i>Aquila chrysaetos</i>	✓	
Golden Oriole	<i>Oriolus kundoo</i>	✓	
Himalayan Griffon	<i>Gyps himalayensis</i>	✓	
Himalayan Snowcock	<i>Tetraogallus himalayensis</i>	✓	✓
Lammergeier	<i>Gypaetus barbatus</i>	✓	
Long-Legged Buzzard	<i>Buteo rufinus</i>	✓	
Northern House Martin	<i>Delichon urbicum</i>	✓	
Northern Wheatear	<i>Oenanthe oenanthe</i>	✓	
Red-Breasted Goose	<i>Branta ruficollis</i>	✓	
Rock Sparrow	<i>Petronia petronia</i>		✓
Ruddy Shelduck	<i>Tadorna ferruginea</i>	✓	
Steppe Eagle	<i>Aquila nipalensis</i>	✓	
Shikra	<i>Tachypiza badia</i>		✓
White Wagtail	<i>Motacilla alba</i>	✓	
White-Winged Snowfinch	<i>Montifringilla nivalis</i>	✓	✓
Yellow-Billed Chough	<i>Pyrrhocorax graculus</i>	✓	✓

Appendix IV: Other species of interest recorded by camera trap.

Himalayan snowcock recorded by camera traps BE-07 / BE-13 / BE-14 / BE-18 / BE-34 /

Yellow-billed chough recorded by camera traps BE-07 / BE-19 / BE-20

Rock sparrow recorded by camera trap BE-07, Shikra recorded by camera trap BE-34, White-winged snowfinch recorded by camera trap BE-3.

